

FRAMEWORK CONTRACT SMART 2019/0024 LOT 2 - EXPLORING, DOCUMENTING AND ANALYSING DIGITAL POLICY ISSUES

5G SUPPLY MARKET TRENDS

Background Paper

Second Stakeholder Workshop on May 19th 2021

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12.05.2021

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1 INTRODUCTION

5G is one of the key technologies and infrastructure for the industrial and digital transformation. The development and diffusion of 5G, which is driven by enabling a broad range of new services and applications for key industrial sectors, is based on a number of technological developments, in which a disaggregation of hardware and software as well as network-function virtualization and containerization are key trends that allow for radical architectural changes across mobile network domains.

The importance of 5G infrastructure, its fast roll-out and technological capabilities, as well as the development of the supply side of 5G infrastructure, has been highlighted by the European Commission in various initiatives and strategies including the Communication "5G Action Plan for Europe" and the European 5G Observatory. The European Commission also considers 5G as one of five priority areas for standard-setting measures.

However, although Europe is leading in trial investments in 5G, overall infrastructure investments lag behind other regions and Europe's vertical industries are only just starting to cooperate with network operators to identify valuable 5G business cases. Network operators are confronted with decreasing profit margins and strong competition, while European equipment providers need to sustain their competitiveness.

The aim of this study commissioned by the European Commission, DG CONNECT, is to conduct an in-depth analysis of possible development pathways of the 5G equipment and services supply market. Departing from the baseline analysis of the 5G supply market trends a foresight exercise on key trends influencing the further development of 5G has been developed.¹ Based upon a selection of key trends, which were deemed to be particularly relevant for the future development of the 5G supply market but associated with a very high level of uncertainty in its outcome, the study team elaborated hypothetical but plausible scenarios for the future development of the 5G supply market with a time horizon of 2030. Four scenarios are illuminating potential pathways for Europe, based on different configurations of key technological, economic, social and political factors.

The scenarios consider different possible outcomes of developments, in which the 5G industry is moving from a hardware-centric to a software-centric model, and in which hardware could become mostly a commodity, in which a differentiation on functionalities and performance could come from the software and virtualization, easing flexibility and scale on deployment and operation.

While each scenario presented is deemed plausible, it is important to stress that no single scenario in this study is intended to offer a preferred or even desired future. Each scenario comes along with certain risks and opportunities for Europe.

The impact of the four different scenarios are analysed based upon a review of recent academic literature, market analyses, and more than thirty expert interviews with high-level representatives from Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), vendors, standardisation organisations and relevant associations. Where possible, uncertainty related to any quantitative projections included in the scenarios has been accounted for. However, underlying data and assumptions for many projections are proprietary or unavailable for other reasons, therefore an assessment of these underlying data was not possible. The four scenarios and their assessment should inform policy-makers to develop strategies aiming to strengthen the European telecommunication industry and the provision of 5G infrastructure.

¹ The full analysis of the baseline assessment can be found here:

https://zenodo.org/record/4621102/files/5GSupplyMarketTrends_BaselineReport.pdf?download=1

2 SCENARIOS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE 5G SUPPLY MARKET

2.1 Construction of scenarios

The development of scenarios for the possible future development of the 5G supply market in Europe until 2030 is a key objective of this report. The scenarios aim at enhancing an informed debate among all stakeholders on how to foster and support the development and diffusion of 5G.

The basis of the Horizon Scanning activity was a comprehensive screening of foresight reports, business, industry and policy reports, and scientific literature for trends and drivers influencing the future of 5G supply markets. Our analysis identified 130 factors which were then structured according to a STEEP (society, technology, economy, ecology, policy) scheme. Through the Horizon Scanning activity and analysis of results we identified 28 major trends significantly influencing the future of 5G supply markets.

In order to develop scenarios, different trends had to be selected and integrated into coherent pictures of the future. We therefore followed the well-known approach to construct scenarios as described for instance by Schoemaker (1995). We therefore assessed the identified trends and drivers based on a two-step process conducting an internal workshop and by using an expert survey concerning impact and uncertainty of the identified factors. From a sample of more than 500 experts covering managers, researchers, representatives from intermediaries, policy makers, and foresight experts from different organisations, we received 53 complete responses from experts, assessing 28 key factors in five dimensions.

Figure 1 gives an overview of all trends and drivers assessed according to the impact they would have by 2030 and according to the uncertainty that this trend will take place until that time.

Figure 1: Assessment of trends and drivers²

² Normalised average responses to the assessment of the factors' future impact and uncertainty of development.

Based on the ranking of trends we selected eight trends (mainly those with a high impact and at the same time a high uncertainty) for the construction of a set of scenarios integrating factors from different dimensions. These eight key trends were:

Open and interoperable 5G network solutions

The virtualization of the Radio Access Network (RAN) and the development of new RAN architecture (full virtualization of the native 5G core network, open RAN) sets the path for the implementation of open and interoperable solutions in the network.³ Several initiatives have engaged in an “open RAN” model with the aim to replace a closed architecture linking proprietary networking hardware and software by an architecture based on open and modular interfaces.⁴ Open and interoperable 5G network solutions could provide an opportunity for new players to enter the RAN market, foster vendor diversity, increase development speed and competition.⁵ However, currently the potential benefits and gains but also trade-offs in terms of performance, costs, energy efficiency, cybersecurity, supplier diversity and reliability are controversially discussed in the community and literature.⁶

Emergence and entry of new players

Open and interoperable network solutions are paving the way for the emergence and entrance of new players in the 5G supply market. Initially pushed by MNOs to end their dependency on one or two single equipment provider, new network vendors may enter the RAN market.⁷ The emergence of new actors might not be purely associated with the Open RAN movement, but we will also see new entrants from companies with strong competencies in hardware or software development (e.g. Samsung). New players can enter the supply market at different points, e.g. baseband players, like Mediatek, Unisoc, or software vendors, like Mavenir, AltioStar. Furthermore, there is always the possibility, that new key players, e.g. in the US, might emerge in the mid to long-term.

Increase public R&I investments for EU players

Current European R&I investment in 5G development is low by international benchmarks (APAC).⁸ Increased R&I investment for European players could help the 5G innovation ecosystems thrive.

Challenging environment in Europe for cohesion and scale in public initiatives

Government investments in Europe have tended to be on a national level which creates a challenging environment in Europe for cohesion and scale in public initiatives. Nonetheless, there has been active guidance from the European Union, e.g. 5G PPP, and now also with the SNS JU proposal addressing this challenge.⁹ Some European states have launched national 5G programmes that vary in their extent, whereas others are lagging behind.¹⁰ Existing small-scale programmes focus on research and piloting rather than broader implementation. The European 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G-PPP) represents a 3.5 billion Euro investment in 5G of which 700 million is public investment.¹¹

Policy support for new actors

Funding and financial support for new players entering the 5G supply market could help facilitate 5G deployment and increase the diversity of European 5G supply market actors.

Normalised answer categories are mapped with a mean of 0 and standard deviation of 1 as follows: No/very little impact (-2.2), Some impact (-1.0), Strong impact (0.1), Very strong impact (1.3); No/very little uncertainty (-1.2), Some uncertainty (0), Strong uncertainty (1.2), Very strong uncertainty (2.4).

³ Pujol et al. (2020b).

⁴ Plantin (2021).

⁵ Pujol et al. (2020b); Hofer (2020).

⁶ See for instance Barford (2021).

⁷ Pujol et al. (2020a); Pujol et al. (2020b).

⁸ Taga et al. (2021).

⁹ See the SNS proposal: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/news/europe-puts-forward-proposal-joint-undertaking-smart-networks-and-services-towards-6g>.

¹⁰ Taga et al. (2021, S. 12).

¹¹ Taga et al. (2021, S. 12).

Development of vertical markets and industries

The development of vertical markets and industries opens up future application possibilities for 5G and has implications for future 5G supply markets. The ongoing profound digital transformation of vertical industries, such as health and healthcare, industry 4.0 and manufacturing, automotive and transport, AR&VR&MR and mining, places particular demands on 5G. Intelligent Transport Services (ITS) covering the whole area of autonomous driving and e-mobility are a prime example of a vertical industry with very specific 5G requirements: ITS rely on low latency and high speed communication services.¹²

Along with the development of vertical markets and new 5G use cases, the creation of private 5G networks offers an important new revenue stream for incumbent network operators, vendors as well as new integrators. The creation of new revenues is a key motivation of network operators for network overhaul. However, as much as private wireless networks could drive new operator revenues, the opposite could also come to fruition should enterprises wish to build and/or operate their own networks in, for example, industrial campus or factory settings.¹³ The latest 5G observatory report indicates that private 5G networks are a highly dynamic market under formation, in which vertical industries, incumbent and new vendors and mobile network operators are taking on new roles.

Security challenges in 5G networks

With the rise of 5G, the growing trend of the importance of security considerations associated with 5G networks is expected to continue.¹⁴ This includes threats to availability and integrity of networks, increased exposure to attacks, or addressing requirements concerning suppliers with a high risk exposure.

Agreements on universal standards and open specifications

An advancement of 3GPP specifications and releases along with standard-essential patents (SEPs) could further promote agreements on universal standards. Universal standards could in turn open up the supply market landscape to smaller hardware and solution providers or start-ups and promote the diversity of players in the 5G supply market.

Based on these factors we constructed four coherent plausible scenarios based on a morphological analysis.¹⁵ The four scenarios result from an individual combination of all factors considered and specific projections of their individual outcomes (See Table 1 in Annex 1 for details). We performed a consistency analysis in order to test the plausibility of possible combinations.

2.2 Four scenarios for the future of the 5G supply market with a time horizon of 2030

Based on the above-mentioned development process we developed four scenarios which are being presented next.

2.2.1 Scenario I: Incumbent players driving 5G

Key Storyline: Incumbent vendors and MNOs orchestrate the emerging 5G innovation ecosystem

Incumbent vendors and MNOs are shaping the ecosystem pulled by an increasing demand for new services from verticals which require high performance. Equipment from providers considered to bear security risks is used outside the core network in non-sensitive areas only. The adoption of Open RAN for specific applications and in specific regions set incentives for established vendors to further improve efficiency of their proprietary solutions which allows them to stay competitive in an increased competitive market. Incumbent network equipment vendors continue to operate successfully but new equipment providers are emerging, further facilitating network integration and contributing to an increasingly competitive 5G Open RAN environment. Cloud RAN and vRAN are important intermediate step of MNOs in their investment paths and are able to fulfil the performance requirements in the short and medium term. In the short run, Open RAN solutions are mainly applied for niches, but Open RAN does not serve as a game changer.

¹² OECD (2019).

¹³ GSMA (2020).

¹⁴ European Commission (2019).

¹⁵ See for instance Johansen (2018).

2.2.2 Scenario II: Slow pace of 5G Roll-Out

Key Storyline: Modest demand by consumers and industries and inconsistent implementation of cyber-security requirements in Europe hampers a fast 5G diffusion

In this scenario MNOs and vertical industries are struggling to find the right business case for 5G. Consumers are indifferent towards higher broadband speeds offered by highly priced 5G networks and are served over a wide area with 4G. 5G-based industrial services only emerge slowly. A fragmented approach to the implementation of cybersecurity requirements in Europe leads to legal uncertainty with regard to supplier requirements and long transition periods for updated multi-vendor strategies. At the same time, conditions for increasing multi-vendor interoperability of standards-based interfaces are not being reached in the medium term. As a result, 5G deployment in Europe in consumer and business markets is of modest speed. MNOs slowly start providing end-to-end Open RAN networks, primarily in suburban and rural areas.

2.2.3 Scenario III: Open RAN as game changer

In this scenario, it is envisioned that technological progress is impressive and Open 5G innovation platforms enable highly standardised services on fully virtualised networks on the medium and long term. The demand for new 5G services and solutions is created by verticals which are served by MNOs (mobile network operators) but also new entrants specialised in operating networks. Established MNO, incumbent vendors, verticals and new entrants build up the 5G innovation ecosystem and new specific solution such as private networks for factories or solutions for autonomous driving are on the rise. Open RAN solutions drive suburban offerings at low cost and broaden the range of services also in rural areas. MNOs face competition by both new European and non-European operators which enter the industry to serve specialized areas, which in turn, accelerates the interest by verticals. This leads to an increasing differentiation in customer segments. Strong policy support for pilot projects in collaboration with verticals pushes applications in new fields. 5G supply markets are characterised by high levels of competition. As the need for telecom system integration expertise is high, new players, which offer technology-based innovations for digital transformation, are gaining importance.

2.2.4 Scenario IV: 5G for Big tech

Key Storyline: Big tech companies conquer the 5G supply markets with Open RAN business models

Virtualisation of networks and disaggregation of software and hardware change the landscape for network equipment, deployment, and service provision on the long term. The development is changing the definition of "infrastructure" as software can be run on someone else's physical infrastructure and virtualisation and the use of clouds becomes more commonplace. New business models based on Open RAN architectures and interfaces are gaining momentum and new major players (e.g. GAFAM) are entering the 5G supply market. Complete and operational 5G solutions (from hardware to software) encourage companies from vertical industries to enter the 5G supply market. MNOs (mobile network operators) are not able to find their role as infrastructure providers for industrial players. They are outflanked by big tech companies who also offer services to end-users. Big tech companies become the "new operators" by offering carrier-like services bypassing incumbent mobile network operators, thus, big tech companies will serve as virtual operators.

3 SCENARIO IMPACT ANALYSIS

The four different scenarios describe different pathways for the future development of the 5G supply market with a time horizon of 2030. They aim to inform companies, researchers, interest groups, standardisation bodies and policy makers in their decision-making and should facilitate a debate about how to shape the future development of 5G.

In order to support decision-making, an assessment of the scenarios can deliver further evidence for the various stakeholders concerned. Obviously, the different actors and stakeholders of the 5G supply market have also different interests and perspectives. The impacts go beyond a pure market-based dimension and affect issues such as cybersecurity or energy consumption which are also of interest for society at large.

We therefore assessed the scenarios against a number of impact dimensions and took into account perspectives from different market players (e.g. MNOs and equipment vendors) and other stakeholders (e.g. citizens, public policy). For the assessment of the four scenarios we address the following nine dimensions: 1) Market Competition, 2) Costs (CAPEX and OPEX), 3) Business requirement and models, 4) New services and applications, 5) Modularity and supplier dependency, 6) Cybersecurity, 7) Energy efficiency and consumption, 8) Interoperability: standards needs and licensing issues, 9) Overall economic impact for Europe.

As Open RAN is one of the fundamental key trends for the future of the 5G supply market and the development of the different scenarios, the possible development and diffusion of Open RAN was a key element in some assessment dimensions.

For the assessment of the scenarios we referred to more recently published studies and data about the development of 5G and conducted about 30 interviews with representatives from MNOs, vendors, research institutes and standardisation bodies. We explicitly asked about the opportunities and threats for MNOs and vendors as major player in the supply market.

Based on the evidence and judgements collected, a synthesis of the assessment for the four scenarios along the nine dimensions has been established (see also Table 2 in the Annex for a summary). The results of the the scenario assessment thereby highlight the current uncertainty and the diverging assessment and expectations regarding open RAN on the short and medium term.¹⁶ Nevertheless, they point to certain potentials for action and innovation that might become more relevant in the future.

3.1 Impact Analysis of Scenario I: Incumbent players driving 5G

This scenario assumes that incumbent MNOs and traditional vendors will shape the future evolution of 5G in Europe on the basis of current performance requirements in the short term. The opportunity for MNOs in a context of open interfaces is that their orchestration efforts bring increased competition by attracting entrants. However, only the largest incumbent MNOs, with enough R&D activities and financial capacities in place may start to build and orchestrate an incipient ecosystem of new component suppliers. **Market competition** in Europe increases slowly. Incumbent vendors may maintain their market share and play a decisive role in the development of Open RAN.

The emergence of new vendors will by large focus on the increasingly relevant private sector networks. These new networks provide in particular opportunities for new vendors, as there are no path dependencies as in the large European consumer markets. A risk for both MNOs and traditional vendors is that revenue opportunities in these emerging markets may not be seized because of their comfortable position in the large consumer market.

In terms of **costs**, MNOs have found it financially feasible (or even beneficial) to invest in vRAN and Cloud RAN as intermediate solutions and gradually introduce for deploying Open RAN (even if proprietary) in the long run. Traditional vendors anticipate these developments and adjust their prices at least to some extent. As a result, total operating costs at least slightly decrease for MNOs.

Business models and system integration for the supply chain are likely to remain by large unchanged in the medium term. Only large MNOs may feel confident to explore white box models and potentially adopt an in-house model of system integration in the future, while the bulk of European MNOs may not have the capability to test and integrate multiple vendors elements themselves. A limited scale of potential Open RAN deployments would put new suppliers in a less favourable condition to access external capital. They remain reliant on the decisions of incumbent suppliers to include them into their products.

The overall pace of **modularisation and decrease of supplier dependency** is moderate. Despite of a modest overall demand by the vertical business sector in this scenario, a key risk is that their specific QoS requirements are not being matched by existing supply. Open RAN is seen as a driver for differentiation and innovative solutions. Hence, according to this view, there would be opportunities for new entrants to enter the vendor market.

¹⁶ see Barford 2021; Plantin 2021.

The emergence of **new services and applications** in this scenario may only occur gradually as incumbent MNOs and vendors with their focus on hardware may not be the best actors to introduce new services. The decade-old search of MNOs for a 'killer app' that pushes demand for new generations of mobile communication is testament to this claim. For 4G social media and software companies such as Facebook, Google or youtube introduced the services which drove the growth of mobile data. We may therefore expect that services will emerge which are a continuation rather than radical departures from the existing services.

Cybersecurity risks can be largely contained as MNOs and incumbent vendors invest in risk mitigation measures, which also secures market advantages for themselves. A strong role of incumbent vendors and MNOs may also be beneficial for energy efficiency as system performance might be better tailored to integrated stand-alone solutions.

In terms of **standard setting measures**, O-RAN standards set by O-RAN Alliance do complement the 3GPP RAN standards. While this constitutes an opportunity to increase competition and thus reducing the dependency on few remaining suppliers, the threat in this scenario is that the acceptance of O-RAN specifications is too little due to limited involvement of all stakeholders in the standardisation process.

The contribution of 5G will basically be the same as the current contribution of 4G technology to Europe's economic growth – and we assume that in this scenario we will not see a boost to turnover or employment in Europe as evidence also revealed about previous introductions of new mobile network technologies.

On a global scale, a policy driven push for open RAN in specific world regions on the one-hand, and strong competition from Chinese players in other regions on the other, this could mean that such an overall development in Europe could pose a long-term threat for the European industry at large, when both traditional and new European vendors are lagging behind.

Overall, Scenario I reflects to some extent the ambiguity of the perceived impact of Open RAN on 5G supply markets.¹⁷ On the one hand, high expectations are attributed to the approach – from opening up the supply market to new players to reducing existing dependencies on specific suppliers. On the other hand, the long-established players are driving the technology design and standardisation processes.

3.2 Impact Analysis of Scenario II: Slow pace of 5G Roll-Out

In this scenario **market competition** remains the same or even decreases due to exclusion of vendors because of geopolitical motivations and/or security concerns. Due to a low uptake of B2B use cases, the overall 5G market size does not expand and the slow 5G rollout does not provide opportunities for new vendor solutions to be scaled up.

For the 5G supply market, this scenario resembles the status quo the most in terms of **costs**. Compared with the status quo, equipment prices may even increase if no alternatives for equipment providers manage to enter the market and competition decreases.

In terms of **business models for system integration**, the traditional integrated model is unlikely to change in this scenario. Similar levels of **modularity** cause vendor lock-in and hence supplier dependency to persist. The silver lining is that the potential adverse effects from disaggregation are less likely.

New 5G based **services** cannot be introduced rapidly in an environment sketched by this scenario, and segmented geographical markets may further hamper the roll-out of Europe-wide services. When national policy pushes their introduction, the scenario might be an appealing one for health services particularly, but their introduction might also be hampered by a lack of performance and diffusion of 5G.

Compliance with cybersecurity requirements is not such a big issue in this scenario, as this scenario gives more time to reflect about the risks in advance and mitigate them within traditional, integrated systems and clear overall responsibilities.

¹⁷ see Plantin (2021).

Despite of existing **energy efficiency** inefficiencies of 2G/3G/4G networks in comparison to 5G, an overall slow 5G roll-out in Europe could result in an unintentionally beneficial outcome concerning energy consumption as this may delay an overall increase of data usage, which would be very likely in case of an ubiquitous 5G network availability. Relying on existing networks reduces the carbon footprint and may have a beneficial impact in terms of overall energy consumption. Furthermore, single-vendor solutions are generally more energy efficient due to easier system integration and optimisation.

The scenario has negative implications for **standardisation** for both 3GPP and ORAN Alliance due to a lack of feedback from the applications of 5G standards in practice back into standardisation.

The overall **economic impact for Europe** is clearly negative. The slow 5G roll-out in this scenario may be partly be compensated by the favourable conditions for European suppliers of 5G equipment. Nevertheless, the negative effects from a delayed roll-out are larger than the positive effects for European suppliers in this scenario.

3.3 Impact Analysis of Scenario III: Open RAN as game changer

In this scenario, uncertainties of Open RAN are being solved in the medium term, leading to increasing **market competition** and new suppliers in the RAN domain. Innovation incentives in the supply market and search efforts for new business opportunities for traditional vendors are high in order to sustain their market shares. Regarding new vendors, the most plausible outcome from a present perspective is that non-EU entrants lead the take up. In the longer term, there is a threat of re-consolidation, which could reverse the expected benefits.

The **costs** for equipment (CAPEX) go down due to competitive pressures. The level of innovation is high, and so is the scale of deployments. OPEX of Open RAN deployments catches up and may finally even outperform traditional ones.

System integration costs remain a key challenge due to increased complexity. The definition of a viable system integrator (SI) business model is of high relevance, as a 'white box' model based on open source is most likely to gain pace. High uncertainties regarding overall TCO saving bring opportunities for traditional vendors, which could take an early leadership in Open RAN and make sure that new players develop under their leadership.

The market for new **services** and applications is characterized by a high level of competition among network operators and strong demand by verticals, which will lead to low prices and a high willingness for experiments. More suppliers in the vendor ecosystem allow to deploy customized networks for different user groups. The interoperability between European countries facilitates the fast rollout of use cases. Such an environment favours new, data-intensive services (e.g. CAM, IoT and health). However, risks for network outages increase due to a more complex environment.

Supplier dependency decreases and vendor lock-in in the RAN becomes a problem of the past for MNOs, although with a threat of lock-in at cloud or at the system integration level, as modularity increases. High entrance of smaller players poses a threat to supply chain resilience, due to potential disruptions in case suppliers go bankrupt or have to be substituted due to cybersecurity concerns.

Cybersecurity risks are a key challenge. While interoperability increases, cybersecurity risks can also exacerbate as software-based networks with a larger set of different suppliers potentially provide more entry points for hackers, irrespective of the vendor.

An increased heterogeneity of networks makes it more difficult to realise power gains. **Energy efficiency** and energy consumption becomes a challenge due to three main reasons: i) Open RAN may make it more difficult to measure and control energy consumption in each part of the network, ii) Open RAN solutions will consume more energy as designed for flexibility and interoperability not for optimisation and integration, and iii) for same performance and speed, Open RAN will need more sites than integrated solutions. Therefore, power consumption will be higher with negative impacts for CO2 emissions as well. As there is less centralized oversight on overall energy consumption, remedy for these challenges might be difficult to achieve.

Under this scenario, interoperability and therefore **standards** will become more relevant in general. The O-RAN architecture and its specifications would become (defacto) standards for RAN. The O-RAN architecture will attract new

suppliers, which might eventually contribute to standardisation both at 3GPP and the O-RAN Alliance. To handle the complexity, MNOs can opt for a subset of suppliers and proprietary implementations of open RAN solutions

For Europe, this scenario offers some possibilities (new opportunities for European suppliers, MNOs, service firms and in particular vertical industry) but also risks at the same time (dominance by non-European firms). A key risk in this scenario is that EU incumbent vendors may significantly lose market shares, although some other opportunities arise (e.g. entry of new system integrators).

3.4 Impact Analysis of Scenario IV: 5G for Big Tech

In this scenario foreign big tech companies increase their overall dominance in the **market** at both the demand and the supply side. As network functions and elements become increasingly virtual, big tech players may leverage their cloud and software capabilities to move into the connectivity and supply domains with innovative solutions. Moreover, their financial strength allows them to overtake existing players and new entrants.

However, their specific entry to the markets for B2C connectivity and for RAN equipment may be unrealistic. For GAFAM the core network might be more interesting than the RAN, because the core network is easier centralised, and closer to their current skills and infrastructure, based on data centers.

The key threat for market competition by GAFAM is at the demand side. As added value will shift from connectivity itself to the cloud, the future value generation of MNOs is at risk to decline. Another realistic threat is that big tech players dominate the end-user services layer by offering more value-added OTT services, and MNOs remain stuck offering the least profitable part of the chain, i.e., becoming 'dumb pipes'. Additionally, they may enter the connectivity provision market and increase competition.

In terms of **costs**, the impact on RAN-related TCO is low. Tech companies only take over a small part of a base station's processing. However, the higher bargaining power and overall dominance of GAFAM threatens to keep the prices of their solutions high.

Concerning business models and **system-integration requirements** the key threat for European MNOs is that foreign big tech players become the go-to integration option. On the demand side, big tech business models based on their cloud and OTT services help GAFAMs to increase their dominance. While a vendor lock-in for the RAN might be substantially reduced, a new reliance on large foreign players threatens to bring a new bottleneck in the supply chain (e.g., at the cloud level).

New services and applications, the main driver for 5G added value and new revenues for firms, would be dominated by GAFAM. A use case that would benefit in particular in such a scenario is Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM). Another area where use cases may benefit from complementary competences within Big tech companies is health.

As regards **cybersecurity**, the driving force of big tech companies to provide services is not necessarily security driven but profit driven. Big Tech is not necessarily more secure than medium or small tech – but the scale of people reached is likely to be greater. In addition, new cyber security challenges arise in the context of technological sovereignty and the ability to maintain technology supplier capacities in Europe.

Concerning **energy efficiency**, Big Tech might be beneficial for energy reduction because large tech companies already manage energy in data centers although not so significant in the RAN domain as the centralization is reduced in this scenario.

Big tech companies in this scenario become dominant also in **standardisation**; their influence in the O-RAN Alliance might become bigger reducing the relevance of existing player, however, they could also start offering non-O-RAN proprietary solutions. Common open standards and specifications developed under the roof of the O-RAN Alliance allows competition between MNOs in the EU. However, if European MNOs will significantly lose market share, in the long run their influence in standardisation will be reduced.

Thanks to the fast roll-out of 5G and the emergence of a vivid services eco-system scenario IV offer some opportunities for Europe. Studies on the economic impacts of 5G have shown that these are largest when 5G diffuses fast. If Industry 4.0 is a fast-growing use case, it may provide opportunities for Europe's large manufacturing base in particular. Several industrial firms may extend their product range to 5G based services.

But there are also key risks for Europe associated with this scenario. The fast diffusion of Open RAN may allow non-EU companies to take a good part of the MNOs and suppliers market. Given the weak market position of Europe in many software and services markets, it seems uncertain if companies rooted in Europe can make the best out of these new opportunities. Much will depend on the question if non-European firms will operate these new businesses via European affiliates or directly from their home countries.

4 POLICY OPTIONS

For establishing a viable 5G supply ecosystem, a number of systemic oriented policy measures need to be applied. The policy measures aim at mitigating risks of the outlined scenarios on the one hand, while seizing their long-term opportunities on the other hand.

Please note, that these preliminary policy recommendations are not aimed to be tailored to the assessment of the scenarios but remain on a scenario independent level. Therefore, the workshop planned for the 19th of May has the purpose to discuss, complete and specify the policy recommendations.

Following an overall recommendation providing guidance for the development of the 5G ecosystem, we structure specific recommendations for the following domains: 1) Human Capital Development, 2) R&D, 3) Standardisation / Testbeds / Certification, 4) Entry of New Players, 5) Public Procurement, 6) Platform Creation, and 7) Regulation.

The overall recommendation to the EC and the Member States are the following

- It is recommended to the EC and the EU Member States to develop an open and secure 5G ecosystem in the long run, including MNOs, incumbent and new European vendors, software providers including open source communities, and European users from vertical industries.
- It is recommended to promote European digital autonomy and technological sovereignty via the support of collaboration between new and traditional vendors, and a strong approach towards open source specifications.

Human Capital Development

- It is recommended to include the topic, how to design and develop open and interoperable 5G network solutions into the European Qualifications Framework (EQF) being relevant for Master programmes addressing 5G technology due to the existing and further increasing shortage of skilled experts in the EU in particular in comparison to countries in Asia and the US.
- It is recommended to the national organisations being responsible for education to promote the inclusion of open source (development, business models and licensing) in the programmes relevant for Master programmes addressing 5G technology of their Higher Education Institutions (HEIs).
- It is recommended to the Member States to provide incentives for HEIs and Public Research Organisations (PROs) in general and business schools in particular to offer specific management courses, e.g. as mini MBAs related to 5G technology.

R&D

- It is recommended to support R&D projects focusing on the collaboration between large companies and small companies located in the EU.
- It is recommended to provide more R&D funding focusing on 5G and Open RAN through existing programmes, such as Horizon Europe. New R&D funding initiatives should in particular target SMEs or even microenterprises and start-ups.

- In particular, it is recommended to the EC to consider O-RAN Alliance as a relevant actor for the future design of 5G specifications and standards in the 5G and Connectivity Infrastructure, one of the flagship areas of the EU Recovery & Resilience Facility focusing of the 5G network infrastructures to boost 5G network rollout.
- It is recommended to the EC and the Member States to fund the development of regional clusters of excellence in the area of 5G technologies consisting of partnerships between industry, academia, research institutions, open source communities and the private sector.

Standardisation / Testbeds / Certification

- It is recommended to the EC to investigate the compliance of the O-RAN Alliance to the Code of Good Practice when developing standards released by the WTO and also required according to the EU Regulation No 1025/2012 and make proposals to assure its compliance.
- It is recommended to the EC to launch a Mandate addressing the European Standardisation Bodies focusing on O-RAN related standards, e.g. consider the experiences of UK's SONIC initiative.¹⁸
- It is recommended to 3GPP and the O-RAN Alliance to consider a further collaboration starting with a Memorandum of Understanding but aiming at eventually accepting O-RAN Alliance specifications as ETSI standards via the fast track procedure.
- It is recommended to support for open test-beds all stakeholders, incl. for interoperability testing and deployment, and labs related to O-RAN in order to identify standards gaps, to develop new standards, to enhance existing standards or to develop, test and demonstrate standards.¹⁹
- It is recommended to consider certification schemes, e.g. based on a gap analysis of existing and upcoming standardisation mechanisms (such as 3GPP or GSMA) and O-RAN specifications in particular addressing security issues in coordination with ENISA activities under the cybersecurity act.

Entry of new players

- It is recommended to launch 5G/O-RAN specific programmes to foster entrepreneurship in 5G related technologies and business models.
- It is recommended to continue the programme and explicitly open the Enhanced European Innovation Council (EIC) including the EIC Accelerator to applications from young, high-risk, R&D-intensive entrepreneurs focusing on 5G technologies and business models to address the lack of venture capital in the European small business ecosystem.
- It is recommended to support with new supporting schemes start-ups and small companies in developing products relevant for the Open RAN architecture, but also the reintegration of large EU companies formerly active in the mobile communication sector should be incentivized.
- It is recommended to the EC to provide Venture Capital (VC) in the context of the European Innovation Council Fund²⁰ or the Connecting Europe Broadband Fund²¹.

Public Procurement

- It is recommended to fully exploit the potential synergies between pre-commercial procurement and open source related to 5G technologies in a more strategic and systemic way.
- It is recommended to improve the inclusion of open source in general and in particular the 3GPP standards and O-RAN specifications and standards in 5G related public procurement processes, e.g. in the public procurement

¹⁸ <https://uk5g.org/discover/testbeds-and-trials/sonic/>

¹⁹ Koch, C. & K. Blind (2021): Towards agile standardisation: Testbeds in support of standardisation for the IIoT, IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management 68 (1), 59-74.

²⁰ https://eic.ec.europa.eu/index_en

²¹ CEBF <https://www.cebfund.eu/>

directives or the public procurement strategy taking into account the specific needs of open source based SMEs.

Platform creation

- It is recommended to the EC and the Member States to support the creation of open platforms for experimentation, e.g. related to factories using 5G in the context of Industry 4.0.
- It is recommended to the EC to consider the development of a platform, e.g. a system integrator platform that solely relies on European players and that gives different supplier options, especially for smaller operators. In this context, the role of the already existing 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) should be considered.

Regulation

Competition

- It is recommended to check carefully intended take overs of European companies (start-ups) by large non-European companies and establish the option that the EC or the Member States hold a “golden share”.
- It is recommended to check for dumping prices by non-EU vendors and consider involving the WTO or set up counter measures, e.g. an EU fund for EU vendors, to restore a level playing field.
- It is recommended to the EC and the Member States to foster more competition between MNOs, also related to the spectrum allocations.
- It is recommended to the Member States to foster network sharing to push the roll out of 5G.

Security

- It is recommended to the EC to consider the O-RAN Alliance and their specifications and standards in particular in the Cybersecurity of 5G networks EU Toolbox, e.g. in the strategic and technical measures, but also the supporting actions.
- It is recommended to fund security audits of critical OSS projects in the context of O-RAN requiring specific security improving changes with public resources.

Energy Efficiency

- It is recommended to consider the potential to improve energy efficiency via the implementation of 5G technologies in future regulations and standards.

5 ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
3GPP	3rd generation partnership project
AR	Augmented Reality
CAM	Computer-Aided Manufacturing
CAPEX	Capital expenses
CU	Centralized unit
DU	Distributed unit
EIC	European Innovation Council
EPC	Evolved packet core
ETSI	Organization for European Standards
GAFAM	Google, Amazon, Facebook, Apple and Microsoft
GSMA	Groupe Speciale Mobile Association
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IoT	Internet of Things
MIMO	Multiple-in, Multiple-out
mmWave	Milimeter Wave
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
OPEX	Operational expenses
O-RAN	Open RAN: disaggregated RAN functionality built using open interface specifications between elements. Can be implemented in vendor-neutral hardware and software-defined technology based on open interfaces and community-developed standards.
O-RAN Alliance	O-RAN Alliance is a specification group defining next generation RAN infrastructures, adhering to the principles of intelligence and openness.
OSS	Operations support system
PRO	Public Research Organisation
QoS	Quality of service
RAN	Radio Access Network
TCO	Total cost of ownership
TIP	Telecom infra project
VC	Venture Capital
VR	Virtual reality
vRAN	Virtual RAN: an implementation of the RAN in a more open and flexible architecture which virtualizes network functions in software platforms based on general purpose processors.

6 REFERENCES

- Barford, J. (2021). The push for OpenRAN: Careful what you wish for. ENDER ANALYSIS(20 April 2021). Retrieved from <https://www.endersanalysis.com/reports/push-openran-careful-what-you-wish>
- European Commission (2019). Member States publish a report on EU coordinated risk assessment of 5G networks security: Press corner.
- ENISA (2020). New Guidelines for Telecom and 5G Security. Retrieved from: <https://www.enisa.europa.eu/news/enisa-news/new-guidelines-for-telecom-and-5g-security>.
- European Union (2019). Regulation (EU) 2019/881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on ENISA (the European Union Agency for Cybersecurity) and on information and communications technology cybersecurity certification and repealing Regulation (EU) No 526/2013 (Cybersecurity Act). Official Journal of the European Union.
- GSMA (2020), Network Economics Annual Report 2020, Retrieved from: <https://www.gsma.com/futurenetworks/resources/network-economics-annual-report-2020/>
- Hofer, M. (2020). Current Status and Outlook on Open Radio Access Network initiatives, Zenodo.
- Johansen, I. (2018). Scenario modelling with morphological analysis, *Technological Forecasting & Social Change.*, 126, 116-125.
- Koch, C. & K. Blind (2021). Towards agile standardisation: Testbeds in support of standardisation for the IIoT, *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management* 68 (1), 59-74.
- OECD (2019). The road to 5G networks. OECD, Paris.
- Plantin, J.-C. (2021). The political hijacking of open networking. The case of open radio access network. LSE Research Online Documents on Economics. Retrieved from <https://ideas.repec.org/p/ehl/lserod/109858.html>
- Pujol, F., Manero, C., Carle, B. & Remis, S. (2020a). 5G Observatory Quarterly Report 8 Up to June 2020, im Auftrag von: European Commission, Directorate-General of Communications Networks und Content & Technology, July 2020: IDATE Digiworld.
- Pujol, F., Manero, C., Carle, B. & Remis, S. (2020b). 5G Observatory Quarterly Report 9 Up to September 2020, im Auftrag von: European Commission, Directorate-General of Communications Networks und Content & Technology: IDATE Digiworld.
- Schoemaker, P.J.H. (1995): Scenario Planning: A Tool for Strategic Thinking. *Sloan Management Review* 36, 25–40.
- Taga, K., Uferer, C. & McInroy, C. (2021). 5G Supply Market Trends: Baseline Scenario Report.

7 ANNEXES

7.1 Annex I: Morphological grid for the construction of 5G scenarios

The following table illustrates how the different factors have been combined into the different scenarios.

Key trends	Scenario I: Incumbent players driving 5G	Scenario II: Slow pace of 5G Roll- Out	Scenario III: Open RAN as game changer	Scenario IV: 5G for big tech
Open and interoperable 5G network solutions	Moderate Proprietary RAN networks dominant, open interfaces are used for specific applications and in some areas (e.g. greenfield investments). MNOs invest in vRAN and Cloud RAN as intermediate solution. Customer demand serves as important pull factor for the development.	Slow MNOs are slowly starting to migrate to 5G Open RAN networks, mainly in suburban and rural areas, interoperability is not fully achieved.	Rapid Open and fully interoperable standards-based equipment and network infrastructure is rendering multi-vendor interoperable end-to-end networks available, in urban and rural areas. Open 5G innovation platforms are thriving the 5G supply market ecosystem with a strong focus on Open RAN products with potential for radical innovation, however, this is a development with a longer time perspective and will not be realised before 2025	Rapid Cloud RAN solutions are broadly introduced, open 5G innovation platforms facilitate digitization among industries. Big tech companies are driving open standard development, though for some interfaces open standards are still not available. Open specifications drive investment by relevant players.
Entry of new players	Low MNOs are using existing vendors but also gradually integrate new suppliers by building up system integration capabilities.	Low European equipment suppliers are preferred through regulation (public procurement) and public R&I investments; new European players are slowly emerging.	High Move from monolithic/single vendor telecom network infrastructure to open cloud and software-based IT solutions. New players widening the industry through broad deployment of small cell networks. While there will be many new entrants from the US and Europe in the short and medium term, a consolidation will happen on the longer term.	Moderate New, often large players enter the supply market and act as the new virtual operators and drive standardisation processes, many European players (especially smaller companies) drop out of the supply market.
Research & Innovation (R&I) investments in the EU	High R&I investments important to assure framework conditions for orchestration and interoperability. R&I investments in relation	Low R&I investments are dedicated to harmonisation of regulatory frameworks	Moderate R&I investments are focused on tailoring 5G networks and services to specific societal needs, as well as at integrating new	Moderate High share of private R&I investments (big tech companies, verticals)

	to 3GPP standardisation processes are substantial	and to support broad 5G roll-out.	technologies (e.g. Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning).	Venture capitalists and verticals are investing in new entrants.
Level of EU cohesion	High The 3GPP roadmap guarantees the cohesions between national deployments. Many European countries have launched national 5G R&I programmes, though the scale of the programs varies from country to country.	Low Government investments in Europe have tended to be on a national level, and there has been little guidance or direction from the European Union. Several European countries exclude specific equipment suppliers.	Low The need for a coordination among European Member States to support Open RAN deployment is modest	High Cross-border coordination is in place, harmonisation across Europe is driven by new big tech business models and use cases, that are taken up by EU policies. This leads to 'cherry picking' of urban areas for Open RAN-based 5G deployment (as data collection is driving big tech)
Policy support for new actors in the EU	Moderate Support of a heterogenous 5G supply market ecosystem, supporting new players, that enable digital transformation; global conflicts are mitigated.	Low Though some European newcomers are emerging, policy support is limited and dedicated to the further roll-out of 5G Open RAN networks in rural areas.	High Policy encourages innovation along the entire supply chain through competition	Low Minor policy support for verticals in terms of informing on cost-sharing models, monitoring KPIs, securing basic services, reducing environmental impact.
Development of vertical markets and industries	Moderate Due to growth of verticals MNOs have the willingness to invest	Low 5G-based industrial services only emerge slowly, which is an important reason for a slow 5G roll-out.	High New entries serve the needs for verticals	High Big tech companies push the development
Security challenges in 5G networks	Low MNOs and established vendors have the capabilities and experience to cope with various cybersecurity issues with the 5G toolbox serving as important instrument.	Low Despite the existence of the 5G toolbox only a fragmented approach to the implementation of cybersecurity requirements is realised.	Moderate New and innovative solutions sometimes reveal new vulnerabilities and security loopholes in 5G Open RAN environments.	Moderate Big tech companies guarantee for security of 5G networks, but do not disclose security matters. Governments have some legal control over companies.
Universal standards and open specifications	3GPP Open RAN specifications are used to build up 5G supply ecosystem by incumbent MNOs and vendors; European players contribute in further developing standards for interoperable multi-	3GPP Open RAN specifications are used to build up 5G Open RAN networks.	Universal standards and open specifications developed by open source foundations are in place under an open-source paradigm, also smaller companies and innovative start-ups involved in standardisation	New consortia driven by big tech companies develop new standards for interoperable 5G innovation platforms which are used to integrate verticals. On the long term, the role

vendor end-to-end network functions.

processes. Risk of fragmentation if proprietary O-RAN implementations start to flourish.

of standardisation might erode.

7.2 Annex II: Impact analysis overview

Based on the evidence and judgements collected, a synthesis of the assessment for the four scenarios with a time horizon of 2030 along the nine dimensions can be made. The synthesis clearly shows a number of trade-offs between the different scenarios, which are portrayed in the following table.

Assessment dimension	Scenario I: Incumbent players driving 5G	Scenario II: Slow pace of 5G Roll-out	Scenario III: Open RAN as game changer	Scenario IV: 5G for Big Tech
Competition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The opportunity for MNOs in a context of open interfaces is that their orchestration efforts bring increased competition by attracting entrants However, if few proprietary Open RAN solutions dominate, this could undermine some of the supplier diversity benefits of Open RAN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Market concentration remains the same or even decreases due to vendor bans Market size does not expand due to low uptake of B2B use cases This scenario threatens to lower Europe's competitiveness 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This scenario is expected to increase innovation incentives, assuming uncertainties are solved. New suppliers emerge and competition in the RAN domain increases. However, the most plausible outcome is that non-EU entrants lead the take up of the market share subject to be disrupted There is however the threat of re-consolidation in the longer term, which would reverse the expected benefits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Foreign big tech companies increase their overall dominance at both the demand and the supply side However, their specific entry to the markets for B2C connectivity and for RAN equipment may be unrealistic
Costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is an opportunity for MNOs to keep the challenging costs of system integration relatively low compared to a scenario where a dominant system integrator appears However, their ability to afford new Open RAN deployments is questioned Lack of scale and innovation may keep OPEX of new solutions high compared to current solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This scenario resembles the status quo the most, in terms of costs Equipment prices may even increase if competition decreases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Equipment costs (CAPEX) go down due to competitive pressures Innovation is high, and so is the scale of deployments. OPEX of Open RAN deployments catches up and may even outperform traditional ones System integration costs remain a challenge due to increased complexity, bringing high uncertainty to TCO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The impact on RAN-related OPEX is low. Tech companies only take over a small part of a base station's processing However, the higher bargaining power and overall dominance of GAFAM threatens to keep the prices of their solutions high
Business models and requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It seems unlikely that European MNOs have the resources to integrate multiple vendors elements themselves Nevertheless, large MNOs feel confident they have the expertise to do integration research, which assuming coordination, the less costly marketplace model would seem feasible 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The slow 5G rollout does not provide opportunities for new vendor solutions to scale The traditional integrated model remains the most dominant one 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In this scenario the system integrator (SI) business model is of high relevance The 'white box' model based on open source is most likely to gain pace Traditional vendors maintain the opportunity to take an early leadership in Open RAN and make sure new players 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The threat for European MNOs is that foreign big tech players become the go-to integration option On the demand side, big tech business models based on their cloud and OTT services help GAFAMs increase their dominance

				develop under their leadership	
New services and applications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Such a surrounding is conducive to the development and introduction of new services, since it offers security and stable relations between MNOs and their retail customers. However, incumbent MNOs with their focus on hardware may not be the best actors to introduce new services. We therefore expect that services will emerge which are a continuation of existing offers rather than radical departures from the existing services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It seems unlikely that we see a rapid development and market introduction of new 5G based services in such an environment. Moreover, segmented geographical markets may further hamper the roll-out of Europe-wide services. Hence, this may be an appealing scenario for health services particularly when national policy pushes their introduction; though, health services may be hampered by a lack of performance and diffusion of 5G 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High levels of competition and new network operators will lead to low prices and a high willingness for experiments in the market More suppliers in the vendor ecosystem also allows to deploy customized networks for different user groups, though, with higher risks of network outages due to a more complex environment Interoperability between European countries facilitates the rollout of use cases Such an environment favours new, data-intensive services (e.g. CAM, IoT and health) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A use case that would benefit in particular in such a scenario is Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM). Another area where use cases may benefit from complementary competences within Big tech companies is health 	
Modularity and supplier dependency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vendor lock-in is reduced as a consequence of a larger set of supplier options available to MNOs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Similar levels of modularity cause vendor lock in to persist The silver lining is that the potential adverse effects from disaggregation are less likely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vendor lock-in in the RAN becomes a problem of the past, although with a threat of lock-in at the system integration level Higher entrance of smaller players threatens to lower supply chain resilience, due to potential disruptions in case suppliers go bankrupt or are removed due to cybersecurity concerns 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vendor lock-in for the RAN is also substantially reduced However, the new reliance on large foreign players threatens to bring a new bottleneck in the supply chain (e.g., at the cloud level) 	
Cybersecurity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> MNOs and incumbent vendors invest in risk mitigation and could thus secure market advantages for themselves 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Gives more time to reflect about risks and mitigate them May provide telco companies time to remain the incumbent actors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> While Open RAN may bring more interoperability, it can also exacerbate cybersecurity risks by provide more entry points for hackers, irrespective of vendor. Each new supplier will have to fulfil cybersecurity requirements Adressing cybersecurity challenges might delay the diffusion of Open RAN 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The driving force of big tech companies to provide services is not necessarily security driven but profit driven. Big Tech is not necessarily more secure than medium or small tech, but the scale of people reached is likely to be greater. 	
Energy efficiency and consumption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incumbent MNOs may be beneficial for energy efficiency because they are incentivized from a cost point of view 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Relying on existing networks where there is a sunk cost in terms of manufacturing and carbon footprint may have a beneficial impact in terms of overall energy consumption single-vendor solutions are generally more energy efficient due to integration and optimisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Less centralized oversight of overall energy consumption The more heterogenous the networks, the more difficult to realise power gains More efficient in the medium term for greenfield networks Open RAN may make it more difficult to measure and control 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May be beneficial for energy reduction because large tech companies already manage energy in data centers although not so significative in the RAN domain as the centralization is reduced The future of Big Tech in 5G is not certain given the anti-trust and 	

			energy in each part of the network	privacy challenges they face
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open RAN solutions will consume more energy as designed for flexibility and interoperability not for optimisation and integration. For same performance and speed, Open RAN will need more sites than integrated solutions. Therefore, power consumption will be higher 	
Interoperability: standards needs and licensing issues	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> O-RAN standards do complement the RAN standards set by 3GPP MNO opportunities exists by enlarging the supplier base and increased competition, thus reducing the dependency on few remaining suppliers The threat to MNOs is caused by too little acceptance of O-RAN specifications due to reduce involvement of all stakeholders in the standardisation process 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Negative implications for standardisation both at 3GPP and ORAN Alliance due to less feedback from the applications of 5G standards in practice back to standardisation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The O-RAN architecture and its specifications would become (defacto) standards for RAN The O-RAN architecture will attract new suppliers, which might eventually contribute to standardisation both at 3GPP and the O-RAN Alliance Under this scenario, interoperability and therefore standards will become more relevant in general To handle the complexity, MNOs can opt for a subset of suppliers and proprietary implementations of open RAN solutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Big tech companies become dominant also in standardisation; their influence in the O-RAN Alliance might become bigger reducing the relevance of existing player, however, they could also start offering non-O-RAN proprietary solutions Common open standards and specifications developed under the roof of the O-RAN Alliance allows competition between MNOs in the EU Service offerings by big tech firms might be beneficial for customers If the EU MNOs will significantly lose market share, in the long run their influence in standardisation will be reduced
Overall economic impact for Europe	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The contribution of 5G will basically be the same as the current contribution of 4G technology to Europe's economic growth 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The slow roll-out in this scenario may be partly be compensated by the favourable conditions for European suppliers of 5G equipment. Nevertheless, the negative effects from a delayed roll-out are larger than the positive effects for European suppliers in this scenario 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers some possibilities (new opportunities for European suppliers, MNOs and service firms) but also some risks at the same time (dominance by non-European firms) Quite uncertainty on the TCO to determine if European MNOs will reduce costs EU incumbent vendors risk to reduce significantly their market share, although some other opportunities arise (eg system integrators) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offers possibilities particularly when European players and new entrants are able to exploit the possibilities due to a changing market landscape European MNOs and European vendors will be strongly threat